

Hydrological recovery of restored boreal peatlands: 10 years after restoration

Päkkilä L.¹, Marttila H.¹, Korhonen P.¹, Menberu M. W.², Kareksela S.³ & Ronkanen A.-K.^{1,2}

¹Water, Energy and Environmental Engineering Research Unit, University of Oulu, Oulu, Finland

²Finnish Environment Institute, Finland

³Parks and Wildlife Finland, Hämeenlinna, Finland

Abstract

Peatland restoration is a key strategy for mitigating climate change and biodiversity loss, yet the long-term hydrological and biogeochemical recovery of restored boreal peatlands remains insufficiently understood. This study evaluates the recovery of water table depth (WTD) and porewater quality over a 10–14-year period following restoration in 27 forestry-drained boreal peatlands across Finland, compared with 19 pristine reference sites. Using a Before-After-Control-Impact (BACI) design, we monitored WTD and porewater parameters including dissolved organic carbon (DOC), total soluble nitrogen (N_{tot}), phosphorus (P_{tot}), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), and SUVA index. Restoration raised WTD and reduced fluctuations toward pristine levels, with median WTD differences between restored and pristine sites generally <5 cm. Porewater P_{tot} , N_{tot} , and DOC concentrations decreased significantly post-restoration, approaching pristine levels in most sites by year 10, although DOC remained elevated in several cases, suggesting legacy effects of drainage. Recovery trajectories varied by peatland type and trophic level, with intermediate and poor sites showing slower biogeochemical recovery. Deeply drained sites exhibited prolonged elevated nutrient concentrations, while drought years (2018–2019) revealed increased vulnerability in restored sites. Our findings highlight that while hydrological recovery can be achieved within a decade, full biogeochemical recovery may require longer, especially under climate extremes. These results underscore the importance of long-term monitoring and tailored restoration strategies that account for peatland heterogeneity and legacy effects.